

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for MPT

ROBOTICS IN PHYSIOTHERAPY

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value added course on
ROBOTICS IN PHYSIOTHERAPY
for MPT 2020

15 week course (30 Hours)

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

0824-2429139

Srinivas University City Campus
Ground floor
Pandeshwar
Mangaluru- 575001

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Course period	From June 2022 till September 2022, during 4 th semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	MPT 2 nd year postgraduates (2020 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide knowledge about current robotic rehabilitation technologies utilized and the role in physical therapy practice.
2. Provide a framework for adopting and investing in robotic technologies.
3. Train to appraise the research evidence across upper- and lower-extremity robotic technologies.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MODULE	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Introduction to robotic technology	5
2	Application of robotic technology in physiotherapy practice focusing on enhancing patient care.	9
3	Evidence based information on robotics and physiotherapy.	6
4	Activity: Appraisal of research evidence across upper and lower limb robotic technologies.	10

Attendance Policy:

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. Craig J. Introduction to robotics. 4th ed. Pearson, 2022
2. Research articles related to robotics in physiotherapy.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

ADAV MOHAK GIRISH (5SU20PT801)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
from June to September 2022 (30 Hours)

Thrishala

Dr. Thrishala Noronha
Course Instructor

Rajasekar S

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

AKSHITHA K R (5SU20PT802)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
from June to September 2022 (30 Hours)

Thrishala

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Course Instructor

Rajasekar

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

ASHWINI BHAT B (5SU20PT803)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
from June to September 2022 (30 Hours)

Thrishala

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Rajasekar

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

ASMITA KADEL (5SU2oPT8o4)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
from June to September 2022 (30 Hours)

Thrishala

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

DAYMA NIKITA OMPRAKASH (5SU2oPT8o5)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

JADHAV MONALI SANJAY (5SU2oPT8o6)

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This Certificate is presented to

JISHA V R (5SU2oPT8o7)

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

JOSHI JAI KAILASH (5SU20PT808)

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

MOKALE PRAMOD PRABHAKAR (5SU20PT809)

for completing 15 weeks value added course on "Robotics in Physiotherapy" conducted
from June to September 2022 (30 Hours)

Thrishala

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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This Certificate is presented to

NIKITHA (5SU20PT810)

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

PATEL DIVYA SANJAYBHAI (5SU20PT811)

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This Certificate is presented to

PATIL GANDHALI JAYKUMAR (5SU20PT812)

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This Certificate is presented to

SAROJ KUMAR SAHOO (5SU20PT813)

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This Certificate is presented to

SHETTY NIDHI SADANAND (5SU20PT814)

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This Certificate is presented to

SHINE T (5SU20PT815)

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

SHRAVAN KUMAR (5SU20PT816)

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This Certificate is presented to

SHREEJA K (5SU20PT817)

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This Certificate is presented to

SOWMYA B (5SU20PT818)

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